

THE INFLUENCE OF PLANTING SCHEMES ON THE BEGINNING OF PHENOLOGICAL PHASES OF AUTUMN APPLE TREE VARIETY GOLDEN DELICIOUS IN THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN

Yusupova Malohat Sadullaevna
doctoral student

Islamov Sahib Yakshabekovich
professor

Namozov Ikhtiyor Chorievich
associate professor

Research Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture and Winemaking named
after Akademik M. Mirzayev, Tashkent State Agrarian University

lhtiyor_8226@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11112337>

Key words: Garden, stock, varieties, apple tree, seedlings, tree, planting scheme, bud, branches, flower, fruit, harvest.

Annotation. The article presents the results of scientific research on the influence of weak vegetatively propagated rootstocks M-IX and MM106 and the distribution patterns of trees of autumn Golden Delicious apple varieties on the development of vegetative and generative buds.

It was found that although the above factors do not have a significant impact on the formation and development of vegetative and generative buds. However, with a thickened placement of trees in the garden, an earlier blooming of dormant buds is observed. With a sparse arrangement of trees, spring budding, in comparison with a thickened planting, is delayed by 2-3 days.

Introduction. It is known that the productivity of any agricultural plants directly depends on the planting scheme. This issue is deepening especially in the intensive apple orchards that are being built on a huge scale in the republic today. Therefore, optimization of tree placement schemes in intensive apple orchards allows full use of the potential productivity of varieties and production of high-quality products.

PQ-52 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 15, 2021 "On measures for state support of the fruit and vegetable industry, further development of the cluster and cooperation system in the network", PQ- of February 26, 2021 Resolution No. 5009 "On measures to implement tasks set in the strategy of agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 in 2021", as well as tasks are specified separately in other normative documents [1]; [2].

M.P. Tarasenko [6; p. 9–15] and is also confirmed by the data of many other scientists, in his special experiments, although the growth period in the XVI graft type began very late in the mother nursery, in garden conditions, the varieties grafted to it died an early beginning of the water period is recorded.

G.M Karakhodjayeva and X.A. Bobayeva's [3; p. 63–67.] In the research conducted in the conditions of the central region of Uzbekistan, the condition and productivity of summer, early autumn and autumn varieties of apples were observed in M-IX grafting. In research, 11 varieties created in Uzbekistan, 5 created in the USA, 14 created in Ukraine, 2 created in Japan,

1 created in Canada, Krasnodar and France were studied and evaluated according to their productivity.

Yakubov M.M, Nazarova D.Q. and others [7; pp. 35–38] studied the following phenophases in fruit apple plants: budding: leaf budding, flower budding (beginning of vegetation); beginning of flowering, total flowering and end of flowering; end of branch growth (end of vegetation). In the study, the period of the beginning of buds and ripening of fruits was studied every other day, the period of flowering - every day, the end of the period of growth of branches, the beginning and end of the period of flowering were studied once every five days. As a result, according to the influence of climatic conditions on phenophases, the beginning of the growing season, and the length of vegetation, apple varieties were recommended for different regions [4; pp. 36–37].

V. I. Senin [5; pp. 11–13] at the institute of irrigated horticulture for more than 20 years, the growth, development and productivity of various apple varieties grafted on M-VII rootstocks were compared with M-VIII and M-IX small rootstocks and the average compared with the condition of these varieties grafted on M-II, M-IV grafts.

Conditions and method of research. The experiments were carried out in the fruit orchard of the Karakalpakstan Experimental Station of the Research Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture and Winery named after Academician M. Mirzayev. Biometric measurements and calculations: carried out on 10 plants in each variant. The experiment was studied in four repetitions.

The experiments were carried out by Kh.Ch. Buriyev and others “Methodology of calculations and phenological observations in conducting experiments with fruit and berry-bearing plants” (2014), “Metodokiya uchetov i nablyudeniy v opytax s plodovymi i yagodnymi kulturami” (1967) by V.F.Moiseychenko in accordance with the recommendations given in methodological literature and the statistical processing of experimental data was carried out by dispersion analysis according to the method of B.A. Dospekhov (1985).

Research results. It should be noted that the scheme of planting seedlings is one of the agrotechnical elements that strongly influence the growth and development of plants. In intensive apple orchards, the correct application of the planting scheme is even more important. Application of the optimal planting scheme for each variety based on the habit of development of its branches ensures normal growth and high yield of plants. The effect of the planting scheme is first of all reflected in the vegetative development of trees. Observing the period of growth and recording of flower buds in apple varieties planted in different planting schemes made it possible to note that there is a certain difference between them. Consequently, in autumn Golden Delishes apple variety, growth and flower bud recording started the earliest in densely planted schemes compared to the control in both types of grafts used. As the planting interval widened, the date of bud recording was delayed by two to three days, that is, in sparsely planted experimental variants, buds were recorded late.

Table-1

Recording of growth and flower buds on autumn Golden Delishes apple trees depending on the planting scheme, 2022-2023

Planting scheme, m	Feeding area, m ²	Seedling thickness, bush/ha	Start of recording of growth	Bloom, date			
				The swelling	25% bloom	50% bloom	The end of

			buds, date	of the buds			blooming
In the M-IX weld							
3,5 x 3,0	10,5	952	17-18. IV	26-29. III	8-11. IV	11-12. IV	16-20. IV
3,5 x 2,5 - наз.	8,75	1143	13-17. IV	24-27. III	7-10. IV	9-11. IV	14-18. IV
3,5 x 2,0	7,0	1428	12-16. IV	23-25. III	5-8. IV	8-10. IV	12-16. IV
3,5 x 1,5	5,25	1900	10-11. IV	21-24. III	3-6. IV	6-8. IV	11-15. IV
In the MM106 weld							
4,0 x 4,0	16,0	625	13-17. IV	24-29. III	5-9. IV	8-11. IV	12-17. IV
4,0 x 3,5 - наз.	14,0	714	12-15. IV	24-28. III	4-8. IV	7-10. IV	11-15. IV
4,0 x 3,0	12,0	833	13-16. IV	21-27. III	3-6. IV	5-7. IV	10-11. IV
4,0 x 2,5	10,0	1000	8-10. IV	20-25. III	2-5. IV	4-6. IV	8-12. IV

The data in the table shows that the date of budding of Golden Delishes apple trees differed somewhat depending on the planting scheme and the type of graft used. In this case, the transition of the budding and flowering phases of trees on the MM106 graft took place 2-3 days faster than the plants grafted on the M-IX graft.

However, it should be noted that external environmental factors and temperature are also important in budding and flowering phases, which may be postponed to one or another calendar period depending on the arrival of spring in the central region of Uzbekistan. Consequently, if, as in 2020, cold weather at the beginning of spring alternates with a sharp rise in temperature (the temperature in the field, which was cold at the end of March, rose to + 24.0 in the second ten days of April), grass of all varieties water buds begin to grow quickly and are written almost at the same time.

In this case, there is no significant difference in the condition of varieties on different grafts. On the contrary, as observed in 2022, if the month of March is slightly cold, the date of recording the buds will be correspondingly delayed, and in such a case, the difference between the graft and the variety in the swelling of the buds is clearly noticeable.

By comparing the data on the start of the growth period in the trees grafted with short and medium-sized grafts, it can be seen that these periods do not match in many respects. A clear example of this is that the growth period of vegetative grafts begins very early in the mother nursery, but this graft does not allow early initiation of the growth period in the varieties grafted to it in garden conditions.

Summary. It should be noted that the planting scheme and the type of graft used affect not only the budding phase of trees, but also their overall growth strength. This is an especially important indicator for intensive gardens that are being built on a large scale today. The establishment of intensive apple orchards in different planting schemes leads to certain differences in the period of growth of trees and flower buds, although they are not noticeable. At the same time, in densely planted schemes, the awakening of buds begins a little earlier. As the planting interval expands, the date of the beginning of the shoots is delayed by two to three days.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. No. PQ-52 "On measures to further develop the system of cluster and cooperation in the network, state support of the fruit and vegetable industry". - Tashkent, December 15, 2021. <http://www.Lex.UZ>.
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. No. PQ-5009. "On the measures to implement the tasks set in the strategy of agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 in 2021". - Tashkent, February 26, 2021. <http://www.Lex.UZ>.
3. Karakhodjayeva G.M., Boboyeva H.A. Study of economic-biological characteristics of new local and introduced varieties for apple orchards in intensive M-9 grafting // State, problems, prospects of interregional fruit growing and viticulture - a collection of articles of the International scientific-practical conference dedicated to the 120th anniversary of the establishment of the research institute. - Tashkent, 2018. - P. 63-67.
4. Namozov I., Yenileyev N.Sh., Ergasheva D. The effect of tree planting schemes in intensive orchards on the growth of autumn varieties of apple and the recording of flower buds // AGRO ILM magazine - Tashkent, 2021. №1 (71) number 36-37 p.
5. Senin V.I., Kovaleva A.F. Produktivnost jabloni na podvoye M9 v uplotnennyx posadkax // Sadovodstvo i vinogradstvo. - 1992. - No. 7. - P. 11-13.
6. Tarasenko M.P. Vliyaniye kachestva posadochnogo materiala na productivity plodovykh nasajdeniy. // Osnovy tekhnologii intensivnogo sadovodstva v Ukrainskoi SSR. - Kyiv, 1978. - P. 9-15.
7. Yakubov M.M., Nazarova D.Q., Boboyeva H.A. The influence of climatic conditions on the transition of phenological phases of intensive apple orchards// The main factors of the development of fruit growing and viticulture in Uzbekistan. Collection of articles of the republican scientific and practical conference. - Tashkent, 2017. - P. 35-38.

